

A Comparative Morphometries Analysis of Zarmayi Catchment Area in Bago Region

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Abstract

This project paper on “A Morphometric Analysis of the Zarmayi Catchment Area” focuses on the different resultant values of stream order, number of streams and stream length of the Zarmayi Catchment Area, based on topographic map and DEM map. In this study, two topographic maps printed in 1944 with a scale of 1:63360 are used. Another map is the raster map extracted from DEM. And then resultant values of basin morphometry vector and raster data are compared. The SPSS software is used for standard deviation and regression analysis.

Introduction

This paper is concerned with the morphometric properties parameters based on analytical methods, which can be classified into two groups; (a) linear aspect and (b) relief aspect. Morphometric analysis has been carried out using Arc GIS 10.1. Collection of morphometric data from drainage networks requires as a first step. The stream network into constituent sub-network is by stream ordering .The Strahler’s (1952) modification of Horton’s (1945) ordering system is the old useful ordering system, and is the one which has been most often used. Therefore, the Strahler’s method is used in this study area to divide the stream orders.

Study area

The Bago (the name Bago was formerly spelt ‘Pegu’) River Basin, a large portion of Bago River including river’s source lies in the Bago Township of Bago Region. The Bago Watershed has an area of 5359.1 square kilometers, and the total length of the main river is 331.5 km. Zarmayi Chaung is the uppermost part of Bago River. It lies between latitudes 18°0’N and 18°26’N and longitudes 95°50’E and 96°10’E. Its basin is 5.3577 sq km occupying northern part of Bago River. It is located in the eastern part of Letpadan Township. (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2)

Figure Region

To

To Basin

(1) Location of Fig

Objective

divide into Zarmayi

compare the Morphometry

Bago Basin in Bago stream

stream order of Catchment Area

results of Zarmayi

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To analyse difference of Zamayi Catchment Area

Data, Materials and Methodology

Extraction of the study area from Topographic Map (85 N /15, 85 N/ 16, 94 B/ 3,94 B/ 4,94 C/1) (1944), lynch Map and Digital Elevation Model (DEM) - Shuttle Radar Topographic Mission (SRTM-3) from United State of Geological Survey (USGS).

Arc GIS-analysis of stream morphometries classification

-Topographic Maps and Strahler's Method (1952)

RS - DEM Map (30 m resolution), Spatial Analysis Tools

SPSS - Regression Method and T-test

CARTO- Map Layout

The study area is first digitized and classified the stream order, the number of streams and stream lengths (in kilometer) are measured by means of Strahler's method. The relationship between the number of streams and stream lengths are analyzed by regression line. The upper part (Zarmayi) of Bago River basin classified morphometric analysis to the same study area, the different because we used different data source and methods.

Procedure for extraction of the Study Area from Topo Map and DEM

To extract Zarmayi stream shape file, Bago Basin area is selected from Topographic Maps (85 N 15, 85 N 16, 94 B 3, 94 B 4 and 94 C 1). And then these selected data are exported with Export data tool. It is used by digitizing, the starting point, the shortest length (0.000314546 km) of first order in Zarmayi Basin in the TOPO MAP. (Fig. 3)

Figure (3) Procedure for extraction of the Study Area from Topo Map

Digital Elevation Models (DEM) is used in order to characterize hydrological networks and surfaces through various GIS tools. It is necessary to familiarize with data in raster format learn about the processes and utility in converting between raster and vector and vice versa, and employ good data management practices. To extract Zarmayi stream shape file, Bago Basin area is selected from Digital Elevation Model (DEM) - Shuttle Radar Topographic Mission (SRTM-3) from United State of Geological Survey (USGS). (Fig. 4)

Figure (4) Procedure for extraction of the Mask Bago Basin from DEM

Result and Discussion

Analysis from the Topographic Map and the DEM for the stream orders

In the Strahler method, Stream ordering is a method of assigning a numeric order to links in a stream network. This order is a method for identifying and classifying types of streams based on their numbers of tributaries. All links without any tributaries are assigned an order of 1 and are referred to as first order. The stream order increases when streams of the same order intersect. Therefore, the intersection of two first-order links will create a second-order link, the intersection of two second-order links will create a third-order link, and so on. Table (1) and Fig (5) First- order is not only the longest in length but also the number of streams is the highest. Fourth- order is not only the shortest length but also the number of stream is the least. Similarity, the number of streams, stream order and stream length are calculated by using spatial analysis tool on DEM data. First- order streams are the longest length because most of the numbers of stream are first order. Table (2) and Fig (6) Finally, as the stream lengths are longer, there are larger number of streams on the DEM and TOPO Map.

Morphometric analyses have been carried out using Arc GIS. The highest order can be assigned to the Zarmayi Basin. The first, second, third and fourth number of the streams order are counted and measured by Strahler (1964) method Table (1) and (Fig 5) and the stream numbers, stream length.

Table (1) Order, Number of Streams and Stream Length (meter & kilometer)

Order	Number of Stream	Stream Length (meter)	Stream Length (kilometer)
1 st	136	1946.83648	1.94683648
2 nd	34	1284.470858	1.284470858
3 rd	9	1015.78836	1.01578836
4 th	1	530.4161657	0.530416166
Total	180	4777.511863	4.777511863

Source: Digitize from the Topographic Map for the stream orders

Figure (5) The Stream Orders digitized from the Topographic Map

Table (2) Order, Number of Streams and Stream Length (meter & kilometer)

Order	Number of Stream	Stream Length (meter)	Stream Length (kilometer)
1 st	42	1122,871	1.122871
2 nd	23	619.927	0.619927
3 rd	10	276.603	0.276603
4 th	5	231.887	0.231887
Total	180	2251.288	2.251288

Source: Spatial Analysis from the DEM Map for the stream orders

Figure (6) Spatial Analysis from the DEM for the stream orders

Regression Analysis on Topo Map and DEM Map

Fig 7(a) Comparison from the Topo and DEM Map for the stream order and number of stream

Fig 7(b) Comparison from the Topo and DEM Map for the stream order and stream length

Fig 7(c) Comparison from the Topo and DEM Map for the number of stream and stream length

Table (3) Results (R^2 & T-test) of Topo and DEM

Name	Topo		DEM	
	R^2	Significant level	R^2	Significant level
Order and Number of Streams	0.8	.109	0.9	.031
Order and Stream Lengths	1	.013	0.9	.054
Number of Streams and Stream Lengths	0.9	0.66	1	.004

Source : based on Fig 7 (a), (b), (c)

Both topographic map and DEM Map reveal that the greater the stream order and the larger the number of streams, resulting in negative relationship between the stream order and number of stream. On the other hand, the smaller the stream orders the greater the stream length and it also results in highly negatively correlated between stream order and stream length. The study of both types of map shows that the greater the number of streams the longer the stream length, and the stream number and the stream length are highly positively correlated. According to regression analysis, if the calculated result is less than 0.1 the relationship between the two variables strong (99.9%), but if the result is greater than 0.5, the correlation between the two variables is weak. The three above mentioned resultant values of DEM map, with values less than 0.1, reveal that the correlation is more stronger than using topographic map.

Conclusion

Drainage basin morphometry of the study area is based upon data derived from Topo Map and DEM. Strahlar (1952) system is used in ordering on Topo Map and spatial analysis tool of stream orders is used in DEM. The two results in the same study area are compared, using two different data sources and methods outcomes result in different results. According to the value of R^2 and Significant level (percent), in comparative study, DEM data source is more accurate than Topo Map data source .If 30 meters resolution is used, it will get a better result on DEM Map.

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